

List of communication output

Home page of the project:

[CLIVAS – Ilmastonmuutoksen riskien arviointi ja sopeutuminen Varsinais-Suomessa](#)

English home page of the project:

<https://varsinais-suomi.fi/en/clivas-project-focusing-on-climate-risk-assessment-begins-in-southwest-finland/>

Newsletter of the Turku-Southwest Finland European Office:

<https://eurooppatoimisto.turku.fi/a/s/210447588-48e6ab311258768ee694ea30de7843a3/6101369>

International Newsletter of the City of Turku:

<https://eventsnewsletter.turku.fi/a/s/123672110-fa1b59067409d12f8273c11dcf13b4d9/6116552>

Newsletter of the Regional Council of Southwest Finland:

<https://uutiskirje.varsinais-suomi.fi/a/s/60405731-c12afb8fd3c31c0623335a58b341b98c/2295386>

Newsletter of Valonia:

<https://uutiskirje.valonia.fi/a/s/195772418-b2b48caefcf67aef711cbd473821dbac/6102106>